

Study Protocol

Evaluation of systematic reviews of surgical interventions and assessment of the impact of outdated studies on the results

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1. INTRODUCTION

BACKGROUND

High quality evidence is necessary to guide clinical decision-making. Health care providers, public health decision makers are overwhelmed with the amount of new information produced. As stated by Donnelly, « An accurate, concise and unbiased synthesis of the available evidence is arguably one of the most valuable contributions a research community can offer decision-makers ».¹

Randomized controlled trials (RCTs) are considered the gold standard to evaluate the efficacy of an intervention. However, conducting randomized controlled trials in surgery raises several methodological challenges related to the choice of comparator, lack of blinding, complexity of interventions, learning curves, center and care provider effect². In addition, trials usually include highly selected population treated in highly selected centers by highly expert surgeons. Thus, the applicability of results is questioned.

Surgery is a rapidly evolving field. The conditions under which the evaluated techniques were originally performed—such as the materials used, surgical protocols, or perioperative care—may have evolved significantly, even if the technique itself remains in use today. In fact, a study published in the *Lancet* in 2009 mentioned that a surgical technique might “ultimately change unrecognizably” because of the experiments surgeons routinely try during operations. It can be so dramatic and extensive that “it makes it impossible to decide whether the operation is just an evolutionary variation” or an actual novel technique⁴. Consequently, the evidence generated in clinical trials can become obsolete and their inclusion in systematic review and meta-analyses could raise important concerns as they no longer reflect the current conditions under which the technique is done.

A few studies have already emphasized the issue of outdated evidence in clinical research. In their study, Smail-Faugeron et al. (2022)³ showed a change in some meta-analyses results when restricting to trials published in the last 10 years, or to trials conducted after a change in clinical practice. Out of the 295 meta-analyses included in their study, statistical significance was changed in 16.1% when restricting to trials published in the last 10 years. However, they did not distinguish between pharmacological, surgical, or other treatments.

Some fields, like surgery, might even have shorter survival periods due to rapid growth and emergence of new techniques. As mentioned in their study (Barkun et al. 2009), the constant and rapid innovation of surgery is at the core of surgical practice and research, which constitutes one of the factors that complicates any assessment⁴. This shows the importance of lining up clinical practice with the most effective, evidence-based interventions.

However, as mentioned earlier, while RCTs are considered gold standard in clinical research – more specifically for internal validity – they regularly face challenge when trying to generalize their findings. More particularly, it was shown that there is a considerable underrepresentation of RCTs in surgical literature, compared to other fields⁴, as surgical RCTs are not always feasible.

Thus, observational studies, when well-designed, can provide results comparable to RCTs ⁵. These study designs have an important role in contributing to evidence in the field of surgery due to the sparsity of RCTs. As Booth et al. mentioned in their study, RCTs and Observational studies are “partners in the evolution of medical evidence” ⁶.

To our knowledge, no study specifically assessed the consideration of evidence obsolescence in meta-analyses in surgery.

OBJECTIVES

Our aim is to evaluate the characteristics and methodological quality of systematic reviews with meta-analyses published in high impact factor journals in the field of orthopedic surgery and to explore whether “older” studies provide a large effect estimate compared to more recent studies. We will also explore how the results of meta-analyses change when outdated evidence is removed.

2. METHODS

The protocol is written according to PRISMA-P and will be published on Zenodo, open access platform for transparency.

STUDY DESIGN

We will conduct a cross-sectional study of systematic reviews with meta-analysis and we will follow the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-analyses (PRISMA) reporting guideline ⁷.

ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA

We will include systematic reviews with at least one meta-analysis, assessing the efficacy of two surgical procedures, or a surgical procedure to a nonsurgical treatment, in the field of general, trauma and orthopedic surgery. The systematic reviews that included only RCTs, or a mix of RCTs and observational studies, will be eligible.

We will exclude systematic reviews with meta-analyses that included studies reporting safety outcomes only. We will also exclude studies conducted in animal models, studies limited to pediatric population and network meta-analyses (NMA).

Our aim is to create a database with orthopedic, general and trauma surgery journals for future use, but for this study, we will limit the data extraction and analysis to orthopedic surgery.

SELECTION PROCESS

The selection of studies will be performed by two reviewers independently with consensus. Disagreements will be resolved by a third reviewer. All records from the merged searches will be screened for relevance on title and abstract first. The two reviewers will then perform an independent full-text analysis of pre-selected articles. Covidence will be used for the selection process.

We will consider the meta-analysis of the primary efficacy outcome of each systematic review. If the review includes meta-analyses (MAs) for more than one primary outcome and/or more than one comparison of interventions or doesn't specify what are the primary outcomes, we will retain the MA that encompasses the greatest number of trials. In the cases where multiple meta-analyses are equally eligible, ties will be resolved using the following criteria: (1) preference will be given to the MA with the largest cumulative sample size. (2) if a tie persists, priority will be given to MA reporting the greater number of events, when available.

SEARCH STRATEGY

We will search PubMed database. We will be limiting the search to recent studies published from January 31st, 2023 up to February 28th, 2025. We will also limit the search to the best relevant journals according to Scimago: general journals, general surgery journals, orthopedic surgery journals. We also added journals suggested by content experts. Specific research equations will be designed, using the following keywords and MeSH terms.

("Bone Joint J"[Journal] OR "J Shoulder Elbow Surg"[Journal] OR "Spine J"[Journal] OR "Knee Surg Sports Traumatol Arthrosc"[Journal] OR "Knee Surg Relat Res"[Journal] OR "JAMA Surg"[Journal] OR "Ann Surg"[Journal] OR "Int J Surg"[Journal] OR "Br J Surg"[Journal] OR "Am J Surg Pathol"[Journal] OR "World J Emerg Surg"[Journal] OR "J Trauma Acute Care Surg"[Journal] OR "Burns Trauma"[Journal] OR "N Engl J Med"[Journal] OR "BMJ"[Journal] OR "Nat Rev Dis Primers"[Journal] OR "JAMA"[Journal] OR "Lancet"[Journal] OR "Annu Rev Med"[Journal] OR "J Exp Med"[Journal] OR "J Clin Oncol"[Journal] OR "Nature"[Journal] OR "Cochrane Database Syst Rev"[Journal]) AND ((surgery) OR (surgeries) OR (operative) OR (surgical) OR (operation) OR (operating room) OR (operating theater) OR (operating theatre) OR (resection) OR (resections) OR (perioperative) OR (peri operative) OR (wounds and injuries) OR (orthopedic procedures) OR (general surgery) OR (bariatric) OR (colorectal) OR (robotic surgery) OR (laparoscopy) OR (laparoscopic) OR (arthroplasty) OR (arthroplasties) OR (orthopedic) OR (orthopaedic) OR (hip replacement) OR (knee replacement) OR (wounds and injuries[MeSH Terms]) OR (Orthopedic Procedures[MeSH Terms]) OR (General Surgery[MeSH Terms]) OR (Acute Care Surgery[MeSH Terms]) OR (Colorectal Surgery[MeSH Terms]) OR (Surgical Procedures, Operative[MeSH Terms]) OR (Robotic Surgical Procedures[MeSH Terms]) OR (Laparoscopy[MeSH Terms])) Filters: Systematic Review, from 2023/1/31 - 2025/2/28

And

("Am J Sports Med"[Journal] OR "J Bone Joint Surg Am"[Journal] OR "J Arthroplasty"[Journal] OR "Clin Orthop Relat Res"[Journal] OR "Arthroscopy"[Journal] OR "EFORT Open Rev"[Journal]) AND ((surgery) OR (surgeries) OR (operative) OR (surgical) OR (operation) OR (operating room) OR (operating theater) OR (operating theatre) OR (resection) OR (resections) OR (perioperative) OR (peri operative) OR (wounds and injuries) OR (orthopedic procedures) OR (general surgery) OR (bariatric) OR (colorectal) OR (robotic surgery) OR (laparoscopy) OR (laparoscopic) OR (arthroplasty) OR (arthroplasties) OR (orthopedic) OR (orthopaedic) OR (hip replacement) OR (knee replacement) OR (wounds and injuries[MeSH Terms]) OR (Orthopedic Procedures[MeSH Terms]) OR (General Surgery[MeSH Terms]) OR (Acute Care Surgery[MeSH Terms]) OR (Colorectal Surgery[MeSH Terms]) OR (Surgical Procedures, Operative[MeSH Terms]) OR (Robotic Surgical Procedures[MeSH Terms]) OR (Laparoscopy[MeSH Terms]))

DATA EXTRACTION

We will develop and pilot test a data extraction form. We will use Google form for data extraction, transferred to an Excel file. Extracted data are presented in the appendix table.

We will extract data on three levels: (1) from the systematic review, (2) from the chosen meta-analysis, (3) from the primary studies included in the chosen meta-analysis. We will also assess the methodology of each included systematic review using AMSTAR 2 ⁸.

Concerning the systematic review, we will extract general characteristics (author name, publication year, journal, DOI), study design of eligible studies included, risk of bias assessment, methods for data synthesis etc.

Concerning the chosen meta-analysis, we will extract the research question PICO (participant, intervention, control and outcome), number of studies included, design of studies included, range of publication dates for the included studies, results (effect estimates with confidence intervals, heterogeneity, direction etc.)

Concerning the different studies included in the chosen meta-analysis, we will extract the general characteristics number of participants, and all necessary results needed to reproduce the meta-analysis.

The extraction of data will be performed by the two reviewers, independently, with consensus. Disagreements will be resolved by a third reviewer.

More details can be found in the appendix.

STEERING COMMITTEE

To evaluate whether the studies are outdated, a Steering Committee of methodologists and content experts, consisting of orthopedic surgeons, was formed. With their expertise, we decided to use prespecified fixed cutoff dates for this study: 2000, 2010 and 2015. These cutoff dates will be used for our analysis.

3. DATA SYNTHESIS

DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS

We will perform descriptive statistics. Systematic reviews characteristics will be summarized using frequencies and percentages for categorical variables and medians with interquartile range for continuous variables. Results will be presented in tables and plots. Statistical analysis will be performed in R version 4.5.0 (2025-04-11).

REPERFORMED META-ANALYSES

We will then redo the different MAs excluding studies according to the cutoff.

For each MA, we will estimate the summary effect estimates under four conditions: (1) including all eligible studies, (2) excluding studies with a reported end date before 2015, (3) excluding studies with a reported end date before 2010, and (4) excluding studies with a reported end date before 2000. When individual study data are available in the original meta-analyses (eg, means, SDs and sample sizes, or the number of events and sample sizes), we will use them to estimate the summary effect estimates using the same effect model (Fixed/Random), and the IV method. If these details are not available, we will pool the studies' effect measures (eg, ORs) using the IV method.

To estimate the impact of removing studies published before a cutoff date, we will calculate the rate of evolution between effect estimates with and without these studies. Effect estimates evolution rates will be calculated as $(EE[without\ older\ studies] - EE[all\ studies]) / (EE[with\ all\ studies]) \times 100$. To standardize the direction of the results, the results of MA will be inverted when necessary (EE^{-1} for relative measures and $-EE$ for absolute measures).

To compare effects before and after a cutoff date, we will conduct subgroup meta-analyses within each MA stratifying studies based on whether their end date falls before or after the cutoff date. For each subgroup, a separate pooled effect estimate will be computed. For MA using relative effect measures, we will quantify the difference between subgroups by calculating the ratio of effect estimates. For absolute effect measures, we will compute the difference in effect estimates between subgroups. The differences between subgroups will then be pooled using the IV method stratifying on the type of effect measure (eg. OR, Mean differences).

We will use the date of the end of recruitment of each primary study for this analysis. When this date is not available, we will impute it by calculating the median of time between publication date and end of recruitment date from the available primary studies. We will have one different median for each meta-analysis. Forest plots with studies included in the reperformed meta-analyses will be presented, to compare results after excluding studies according to the 3 different cutoffs.

Statistical analysis will be performed in R version 4.5.0 (2025-04-11) using the Meta package version 8.1.0

5. TIMELINE FOR THE STUDY

When do we aim to complete each stage of the review

Research question and protocol	1 month
Literature search and screening	1 month
Data extraction	1 month
Statistical analysis	1 month
Manuscript preparation	2 months

6. BIBLIOGRAPHY

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7. Page M J, McKenzie J E, Bossuyt P M, Boutron I, Hoffmann T C, Mulrow C D et al. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews *BMJ* 2021; 372 :n71
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Data to extract

CHARACTERISTICS OF THE SYSTEMATIC REVIEWS		
General characteristics	Publication year	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 2023 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 2024 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 2025
	Journal	List to choose from: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> JAMA Surgery <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Annals of Surgery <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> International Journal of Surgery <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> BJS <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> American J of surgical pathology <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> World Journal of Emergency Surgery <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Journal of trauma and acute care surgery <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Burns and trauma <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Bone and Joint Journal <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Journal of Shoulder and Elbow Surgery <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Spine Journal <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Knee surgery sports traumatology, arthroscopy <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Knee surgery related research <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> American Journal of Sports Medicine <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> JBJS - The Journal of Bone and Joint Surgery <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Journal of Arthroplasty <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> CORR - Clinical Orthopedics and related research <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Arthroscopy - Journal of Arthroscopic and Related Surgery <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> EFORT Open Reviews <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NEJM <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> BMJ <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Nature <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Nature review disease primers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> JAMA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Lancet <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Annual Review of Medicine <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Journal of Experimental Medicine <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Journal of Clinical Oncology <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Cochrane Database Syst Rev
DOI		
Search date restriction		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes: specify date

Search date		<i>date - DD/MM/YYYY</i>
Primary Outcome(s)		
Type of eligible studies		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> RCTs only <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> RCTs and observational studies
Number of RCTs included in review		
Number of OS included in review		
Total sample size of studies included in review		
Risk of bias assessment	Assessed	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> For RCTs only <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> For RCTs and OS with different tools <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> For RCTs and OS with the same tool
	Tool used for RCTs	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Cochrane RoB tool <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Jadad scale <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Downs and Black tool <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Personal scale <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other
	Tools used for OS	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Newcastle-Ottawa scale <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ROBINS-I <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> MINORS <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Downs and Black tool <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Personal scale <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other
	If other, specify	
Results	Type of studies included in SR	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> RCTs only <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> RCTs and Observation studies
	Oldest study included in SR	<i>publication date - DD/MM/YYYY or MM/YYYY or YYYY</i>
	Most recent study included in SR	<i>publication date - DD/MM/YYYY or MM/YYYY or YYYY</i>
Methodology	Did they consider OS by default at higher RoB compared to RCT?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
	Eligible OS types specified in the inclusion criteria?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
	If RCT+OS included, did they provide a justification to include OS?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
	If yes, choose the reported reason	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sparse RCTs available <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> RCT difficult to perform <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Safety (adverse events) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Rare outcomes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Long-term outcomes

		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not reported <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> other: specify
	Data synthesis method for OS and RCTs	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pooled in the same MA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Analyzed separately (RCTs alone and OS alone) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Only RCTs were pooled in a MA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Only OS were pooled in a MA

SR information needed for AMSTAR 2:

Did the research questions and inclusion criteria for the review include the components of PICO?
Did the report of the review contain an explicit statement that the review methods were established prior to the conduct of the review and did the report justify any significant deviations from the protocol?
Did the review authors explain their selection of the study designs for inclusion in the review?
Did the review authors use a comprehensive literature search strategy?
Did the review authors perform study selection in duplicate?
Did the review authors perform data extraction in duplicate?
Did the review authors provide a list of excluded studies and justify the exclusions?
Did the review authors describe the included studies in adequate detail?
Did the review authors use a satisfactory technique for assessing the risk of bias (RoB) in individual studies that were included in the review?
Did the review authors report on the sources of funding for the studies included in the review?
If meta-analysis was performed did the review authors use appropriate methods for statistical combination of results?
If meta-analysis was performed, did the review authors assess the potential impact of RoB in individual studies on the results of the meta-analysis or other evidence synthesis?
Did the review authors account for RoB in individual studies when interpreting/ discussing the results of the review?
Did the review authors provide a satisfactory explanation for, and discussion of, any heterogeneity observed in the results of the review?
If they performed quantitative synthesis did the review authors carry out an adequate investigation of publication bias (small study bias) and discuss its likely impact on the results of the review?
Did the review authors report any potential sources of conflict of interest, including any funding they received for conducting the review?

CHARACTERISTICS OF THE CHOSEN META-ANALYSES		
MA chosen for experts	<i>(copy the title of forest plot to recognize the MA)</i>	
MA chosen according to	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 1. Primary Outcome <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 2. Biggest number of studies <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 3. Biggest cumulative sample size <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 4. Biggest number of events <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other: specify	
Population	Open question	
Intervention	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> List + Open description	
Comparator	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> List + Open description	
Outcomes evaluated	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> List + Open description	
Follow-up time (timepoint for measurement of outcome)	Time:	
Number of studies included in meta-analysis	#	
Type of studies included in the chosen MA?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> RCTs only <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> RCTs and Observation studies	
Number of RCTs included in chosen MA	#	
Number of OS included in chosen MA	#	
Range of publication years of studies included in meta-analysis	Oldest date: Most recent date:	
Results	Effect measure type	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OR <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> RR <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> MD <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SMD <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> logOR
	Effect estimate	
	95% Confidence Interval	
	Heterogeneity	I-square:
	Direction	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Favors intervention <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Favors comparator

CHARACTERSITICS OF THE INDIVIDUAL STUDIES

General characteristics	First author		
	Publication year		
	Start year		
	End year		
	Study design as reported		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> RCT <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Observational - Prospective Cohort - Retrospective Cohort - Case-control - Other
DOI			
Results	Effect measure type		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OR <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> RR <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> MD <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SMD <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> logOR
	Intervention group	Total N	
		Events	
		Mean	
		SD	
	Control group	Total N	
		Events	
		Mean	
		SD	
	Effect estimate		
95% Confidence Interval			

Interventions and control:

Intervention	Comparator
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Laparoscopic surgery <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Open surgery <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Robotic surgery <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ACL reconstruction technique <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Open reduction and internal fixation (ORIF) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> External fixation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Damage control surgery <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Rib fixation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Arthroplasty technique <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Hip replacement approach <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Spinal surgery technique <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pharmacological treatment <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Rehabilitation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Rotator cuff repair technique <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Surgical technique <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Corticosteroid injection <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Laparoscopic surgery <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Open surgery <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Robotic surgery <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ACL reconstruction technique <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Open reduction and internal fixation (ORIF) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> External fixation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Damage control surgery <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Rib fixation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Arthroplasty technique <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Hip replacement approach <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Spinal surgery technique <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pharmacological treatment <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Rehabilitation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Rotator cuff repair technique <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Surgical technique <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Corticosteroid injection <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other

Outcomes:

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pain score <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Quality of life <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Range of motion, mobility score <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Radiological outcome <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Recurrence <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Mortality <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Implant survival <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Reoperation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Non-healing <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Adverse events <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Length of hospital stay <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Return to sports <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other: specify
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